

METHODS OF CREATING AND USING WEB APPLICATIONS IN THE FORMATION OF INFORMATION FLOW

Umida Reimbaeva Aytbay qizi

Student of Tashkent University Information Technologies
reimbaevaumiida@gmail.com

Nargiza Allambergenova Azat qizi

Student of Tashkent University Information Technologies
naraallambergenova@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This article is about the methods of creating and using web applications in the formation of the flow of information.

Keywords: *Economics, commercial banks, information flow, financial system, innovative technologies, web applications, IT technologies, programming, application development, web-developer*

INTRODUCTION

Today, in almost all aspects of the life of our society, processes of globalization, that is, in every field, huge developments and innovations are being created and the world is seeing the face of it. In science and education, economy, culture, international relations, etc., we can see news created by new innovative technologies or established on the basis of projects based on innovative ideas. is also increasing. Also, this process is widely used in the economy as well as in all areas. At the core of these processes lies the concept of "information", which is considered the greatest power for the 21st century. In fact, today whoever has the most accurate, fastest, most reliable and most truthful information can freely share it with the people around them. Let's take a look at the economic system of our country as a clear proof of our idea. Therefore, the role of these technologies in forming the flow of information, establishing a quality information exchange and continuing this process in a quality way is very incomparable even in ordinary commercial banks. In general, every moment of human life has already adapted to live relying on various such gadgets. This means that every type of activity in people's lives or service sector is covered by these innovative, new and most importantly efficient high-speed devices.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

If we look at it from this point of view, in the creation, discovery and implementation of IT devices, mature specialists in this field are growing: programmers, specialists working in the IT field, bloggers, SMM specialists, web designers, web developers, graphic designers, etc. Web Developers, who create web programs and web applications for any industry, have their place among these information world professions. That is, web developers are internet professionals who create convenient, fast, diverse mobile applications with various advantages that are necessary for all industries. The essence of this profession is that web developers create new application projects and improve them.

Some of the most important terms that a Web Developer should know are:

1. An algorithm is a set of steps to perform certain tasks. In computer programming, algorithms are an important part of problem solving. When creating an algorithm, developers document all the necessary steps to solve a problem and what each step involves.

API - Application Programming Interface. An API allows two different programs to communicate with each other by providing some part of the website's code to developers. Developers can use this code, the API, to create tools and widgets that connect to this website. For example, you use the Google API to enable Google registration on your site.

3. App or Application: You are undoubtedly familiar with applications and use several of them every day. Application is basically a program that allows the user to perform various tasks. For example, Telegram is also an application. As a developer, you need to understand the difference between desktop apps, mobile apps, and web apps.

4. Frontend: The front end of the website is the part that the user sees and uses. Frontend languages include HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, all of which control the appearance of a website.

5. Backend: The code that runs on the server side of the website is called the backend code. The backend contains all the logic behind the site, including inserting, editing, and deleting data in the database.

Whether we like it or not, mobile applications (apps) are used more than websites and they are gaining more popularity than websites. Therefore, the cost of mobile application development is much higher compared to website development.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Mobile applications are made on the basis of two giants: Android and iOS. In order to prepare a program for each of them, you need to have skills and knowledge in

a certain direction. Seeing that the demand for programmers who write applications only for Android or only iOS is very high, one can imagine the demand for a programmer who can write applications for both Android and iOS.

Creating a fully dynamic website using only HTML/CSS and JavaScript is a difficult task. But building mobile apps using relatively easy-to-learn skills like HTML/CSS and JS seems almost impossible compared to building websites. In addition, developing applications for mobile devices is a much more expensive and valuable skill than developing websites.

Web applications are created on the basis of JavaScript, CSS and HTML5 programming languages. Unlike mobile apps, there is no standard software development kit for building web apps. However, developers have access to templates. Compared to mobile apps, web apps are generally faster and easier to build, but are much simpler in terms of features. If you're willing to learn HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, this free tutorial is more than enough to make a fully dynamic website using only HTML/CSS and JavaScript. But building mobile apps using relatively easy-to-learn skills like HTML/CSS and JS seems almost impossible compared to building websites. In addition, developing applications for mobile devices is a much more expensive and valuable skill than developing websites.

CONCLUSION

Web apps require an active internet connection to run, while mobile apps can run offline. Mobile apps have the advantage of being faster and more efficient, but they require the user to constantly download updates. Web applications update themselves.

Unlike regular web apps (and similar to native mobile apps), advanced web apps work offline and load very quickly. This is primarily due to the improvement of the modern browser: thanks to the Application Cache feature, websites can now store large amounts of data offline. That's why advanced web apps can be used without an internet connection, giving them typical native mobile app functionality, such as push notifications, local video and audio recording, and local video playback.

Just like standard web apps, progressive web apps require no download or installation. In many ways they seem to offer the best of both worlds. As Alex Russell, who coined the term, defines them as follows: PWAs are "responsive, connection-agnostic, app-like, novel, secure, discoverable, linkable, installable, and linkable web experiences".

In conclusion, based on this sequence and order, you can easily create a web application, add new functions to it, using the programming language of your choice, in order to form a reliable and high-quality flow of information both in the economy and in commercial banks. and of course you will be able to improve it.

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